

Unveiling the Nexus between Job Characteristics, Organisational Support Perception and Librarians' Commitment to Service Delivery

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Abstract

Librarians play a crucial role in facilitating access to information and knowledge within organisations and society. Their commitment to their work significantly impacts the quality of services provided to patrons. This paper investigated librarians' commitment to service from the perspectives of job characteristics and organisational support perception. The study adopted a survey research design. A total of 400 respondents were surveyed using a reliability and validity-tested questionnaire. Inferential statistics, such as correlation and regression analysis, were employed to analyse the data and ascertain the relationship and effect among the variables. Findings revealed a positive significant relationship between librarians' commitment to service delivery and job characteristics and how librarians perceived support from their organisation. Findings also provide evidence that job characteristics and organisational support perception collectively influenced the commitment of librarians in public university libraries ($Adj.R^2 = 0.245$, $F(2, 397) = 65.671$, $p < 0.05$). However, organisational support perception contributed more to librarians' commitment than job characteristics. The outcome of this study adds to the scholarly debate on the role of job characteristics and organisational support perception on librarians' commitment to university libraries.

Keywords: Job characteristics, organisational support perception, librarians' commitment to service delivery, employee commitment, public university libraries

Introduction

The milieu within which university libraries operate is today characterised by the incessant implementation of innovative technologies like the adoption of digital databases, online catalogs, e-books, and various digital tools that enhance the accessibility and usability of library resources. Also, university libraries face uncertainties amidst increasing expectations and demands from library users (Ogar & Dushu, 2018; Emezie, 2018). In the face of rapid technological changes, evolving user expectations, and increasing competition from online information providers, university libraries are under more pressure than ever to provide high-quality information service delivery to users (Ng'ang'a, Odero & Buigutt, 2020; Sahabi & Otodo, 2021). University libraries must continually adapt and innovate their services to meet their users' changing needs and expectations.

To sustain perpetual competitive advantage in this changing landscape, it is crucial to have dedicated and committed library staff at all levels, sections, and departments. Service-oriented

organisations, including university libraries, have recognised that having competent, knowledgeable and skillful staff is not enough to achieve the goals of the organisation. Without a reasonable level of commitment, these goals may not be realised (Uduak & Cross, 2020; Igbinedion, 2022), especially in today's ambitious world; no organisation can succeed in implementing its initiatives and ideas if there is a lack of commitment among its staff (Obomanu & Akintokunbo, 2019). This highlights the importance of staff commitment in the success of any organisation. Employee commitment refers to the dedication and loyalty of an employee towards their organisation and its goals. Librarians' commitment to service delivery refers to their dedication to providing all library users quality access to information resources and services. Numerous psychology, human resources management, and behavioural sciences studies have emphasized commitment to the organisation and its goals, as it leads to positive work-related outcomes. Likewise, discourse in the field of librarianship, precisely in library management and administration, considers commitment as vital to the effective service delivery of librarians (Ajibare, Fagbemi & Adewolojo, 2023).

Sadly, despite the acknowledged significance of employee commitment to organisational success, both contextual observations and empirical evidence have specifically highlighted the existence of low-level commitment among library staff public universities in South-South Nigerian (Ekanem & Afebende, 2019; Ajibare, Fagbemi & Adewolojo, 2023). Could it be that low commitment level among library personnel is attributed to various factors, including job characteristics and their perception of organisational support? Thus, understanding the factors that influence librarians' commitment is important for library administrators and policymakers to create a supportive work environment that encourages dedication and loyalty, which in turn can enhance the quality of service delivery by librarians.

Job characteristics refer to the specific aspects of a librarian's role, such as task variety, task identity, autonomy, feedback, and skill variety (Adegbaye, Babalola & Alegbeleye, 2020). These characteristics have been found to impact commitment in various private and government establishments. However, their influence on librarians' commitment remains relatively unexplored. On the other hand, perceived organisational support refers to the extent to which librarians believe that their organisation values their contributions, cares about their well-being, and supports their professional growth. It encompasses the support received from management, supervisors and co-workers (Babalola, Alegbeleye, & Adegbaye, 2020). Previous research has established job characteristics as key predictors of employee commitment. For instance, Ahmad (2018) established that employee commitment is triggered through a positive psychological state when certain features of the job are present in the employee's job activities. Likewise, existing empirical investigation have proven that employee perception regarding support through various caring activities from their organisation (either from the top management, supervisor or co-workers) result to them been committed to the organisation and its goals (Ateke & Akani, 2018; Babalola, Alegbeleye, & Adegbaye, 2020). Based on this premise, it is therefore crucial to investigate the effect of both job characteristics and organisational support perception on commitment of librarians in Nigerian public universities.

Objectives

1. To ascertain the relationship between job characteristics, organisational support perception and commitment of librarians to service delivery.
2. To assess the effect of job characteristics and organisational support perception on commitment of librarians to service delivery.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: Job characteristics and organisational support perception have no significant relationship with the commitment of librarians to service delivery in Nigerian public universities.

H₀₂: Job characteristics and organisational support perception have no significant joint effect on the commitment of librarians to service delivery in Nigerian public universities.

Note: The null hypotheses are tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Literature Review

The employee commitment construct has garnered significant attention from scholars across various sectors globally due to its positive impact on organisational work-related outcomes. Conceptually, employee commitment, according to Gumasing and Ilo (2023), reflects the extent to which employees feel a sense of belonging, involvement, and dedication towards their organisation's goals and values. Ibrahim, Maidin, Irwandy, Sidin, Rivai, and Shaleh (2023) portrayed employee commitment as a situation where an employee chooses to stay in the organisation and actively supports the goals and values of the organisation. They further explain that employee commitment entails a sense of duty, genuine inclination, and loyalty towards staying in the organisation. From the perspective of Ajibare, Fagbemi and Adewolajo (2023), employee commitment is the process through which individuals become "locked" into a given organisation and how they react with organisational situations. The commitment construct has three dimensions: affective, continuance and normative (Meyer & Allen, 1997). According to Adegbaye, Babalola and Alegbeleye (2020), affective commitment is an employee's affirmative keenness towards the organisation, which is demonstrated to ensure that the organisation succeeds in accomplishing its goals and objectives. Continuance commitment is the degree to which employees perceive themselves as committed to their organisations, considering the potential costs associated with leaving the organisation (Chigeda, Ndofirepi, & Steyn, 2020). While, normative commitment is related to a sense of obligation or duty towards remaining in a particular organisation (Meyer, Allen, & Smith, 1993). Librarians' commitment to service delivery encompasses ensuring that library resources (both print and electronic), technologies, and services are accessible, relevant, and responsive to the diverse communities they serve.

Job characteristics as a concept has been described differently by several scholars at different times and in different fields of study. In its general sense, job characteristics could be referred to factors or attributes related to the job itself. Harini, Utami, and Putra (2020) posits that the nature of job itself is defined by the degree to which a job offers individuals engaging tasks, learning opportunities, and the ability to assume responsibility. Job characteristics as defined by Wegwu and Princewill (2023) refer to the identifiable and measurable attributes of a job, such as the required knowledge and skills, mental and physical demands, and the conditions under which the work is performed. Specifically, job characteristics refer to the structural features of the job, such as skill variety, task significance, task identity, feedback and autonomy.

Skill variety involves the extent to which a job involves diverse activities that allow employees to utilise their specialised skills and talents (Hackman & Oldham, 1976). Task significance refers to the extent to which a job performed by an employee significantly impacts the lives or work of other individuals within and beyond the workplace (Adegbaye, Babalola & Alegbeleye, 2020). Task identity refers to the degree to which a job requires an employee to carry out a easily identifiable task that results in a visible outcome (Ramli, Soelton, Paijan & Khotimah, 2020). Job autonomy is said to exist when an employee can decide the pace,

sequence, and methods for completing a task (Umokoro & Egwakhe, 2019). Job feedback refers to the degree to which the tasks assigned in a job provide clear guidance and explicit feedback on an individual's performance effectiveness (Hackman & Oldham, 1976). Wegwu and Princewill (2023) noted that the more these core characteristics are present in a job, the more employees are likely to find the job meaningful, feel a heightened sense of responsibility, receive clear feedback about the quality of their work, and perceive the job to have a greater intrinsic value. Similarly, Ngari, Kilika and Muathe (2018) noted that a job that has core characteristics culminates in positive state that drives satisfaction and motivation, which according to Azeez and Abimbola (2016) predict work-related attitudes including commitment.

Several scholars have attempted to conceptualise the construct of organisational support perception or perceived organisational support (POS). It is seen by researchers as reflecting an employee's concerns about the level of support and care provided by the organisation for their well-being, as well as the appreciation for their contributions, efforts, and values within the organisation (Wang, Liu, Yang, & Li, 2018; Kadiri & Elaho, 2020). Additionally, perceived organisational support is an individual-level concept that reflects an employee's personal assessment of the extent to which their organisation values their contributions, cares for their well-being, and supports them in their work. (Suharto & Suprpto, 2023). POS is viewed as a reciprocal relationship between the organisation and employees, where the organisation's commitment to employees fosters feelings of support from the organisation (Zaman, Qureshi, & Butt, 2020).

Extant literature suggests that the treatment that employee received from various members of the organisation, including top managers, supervisors, and co-workers, significantly contribute to shaping their perception of organisational support (Kadiri & Eloha, 2020). Simply put, the perception of organisational support can be evaluated through three distinct levels within the organisation: support from management, supervisors, and colleagues. Supporting this perspective, some researchers (Woo and Chelladurai, 2012; Ahmed, Ismail, Amin, Ramzan, & Khan, 2012; Kadiri & Elaho, 2020; Babalola, Alegbeleye & Adegbaye, 2020) established that organisational support perception can be measured using constructs such as management support, supervisor support, and co-worker support. Accordingly, organisational support is defined as the assistance employees receive from management, supervisors, and peers. This support is anticipated to shape the employees' perception of the organisation's supportiveness, which subsequently influences their commitment to the organisation. Employees develop a positive perception of how they are treated, particularly in terms of the support they receive from co-workers, supervisors, and the organisation as a whole.

Nexus between Job Characteristics, Organisational Support Perception and Employee Commitment

Empirical evidence confirmed strong correlations between job characteristics and employee commitment (Thirunavukarasu & Sritharan, 2016; Ahmad, 2018; Ramli, Soelton, Paijan & Khotimah, 2020; Wegwu & Princewill, 2023). Although the original Hackman and Oldham's (1976) job characteristics theory do not directly address commitment as an outcome, but as an expansion of the theory, there are numerous empirical studies that support the influence of job characteristics on organisational commitment in different geographical regions. For instance, Ramli, Soelton, Paijan and Khotimah (2020) carried out a study on the effect of job characteristics on the organisational commitment of employees in a local IT provider company in Jakarta, Indonesia. Findings of the study revealed that job characteristics have significant impact on organisational commitment. Thirunavukarasu and Sritharan (2016) in their study found a positive relationship between job characteristics and organisational commitment of employee working in Cuddalore town private industries. Their findings also established that

all job characteristics dimensions assessed were significant contributors to organisational commitment.

Another study conducted by Kang and Liu (2018) among university PE teachers in Jiangsu and Zhejiang area in China found a significant and positive correlation between job characteristics and the organisational commitment of university Physical Education teachers. These findings provide clear evidence that the presence of core job characteristics enhances employee productive behaviour, such as commitment to their job and the organisation as a whole. However, report from a study by Putra, Sudja and Martini (2018) on employees of Village Credit Institution in Kerambitan Tabanan, Indonesia, showed contrasting results. The study demonstrated that job characteristics do not affect organisational commitment, while compensation has a positive effect on organisational commitment. The study further revealed that the employees of the Village Credit Institution are not intrinsically motivated but rather their commitment is influenced by extrinsic motivation, specifically the compensation they receive.

Past studies have analysed the nexus between organisational support perception and organisational commitment. Evidence-based studies have shown that if employees perceive support from the organisation, they tend to develop more positive attitudes towards their organisation (employee commitment). Kadiri and Elaho (2020) in their study assessed the relationship between the dimensions of perceived organisational support (perceived employer support, supervisors support and co-worker support) and organisational commitment in selected banks in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. They reported that these perceived organisational support dimensions have positive and significant relationships with organisational commitment. In another study, Ateke and Akani (2018) examined the nexus between organisational support perception and commitment of customer-contact employees of eateries in Port Harcourt. They found that organisational support perception correlate strongly and positively with commitment of the customer-contact employees. Further, the nexus between rewards offered by management and employee commitment is well established in the literature. Evidence from studies also suggest that management can boost their employees' commitment by offering rewards (Newman, Thanacoody, & Hui, 2011; Miao, Newman, Sun, & Xu, 2013). A number of scholars (Falola, Salau, Olokundun, Ibidunni, & Atolagbe, 2014; Osibanjo, Pavithra, & Adeniji, 2014) have investigated the relationship that exists between a financial reward system based on incentives and employees' commitment or attitudes to work. Findings show that benefits have a direct positive link with employee commitment.

In a study carried out by Kang, Gatling and Kim (2014) on the impact of supervisory support on organisational commitment, career satisfaction, and turnover intention for hospitality frontline employees, the result revealed that there was a positive effect of supervisory support on both employees' commitment and their career satisfaction. The study conducted by Limpanitgul, Robson, Gould-Williams and Lertthairakul (2013) revealed that the provision of support from people who share the same work experiences is more effective in helping one to overcome work-related stress as compared to support received from persons in out-groups. Moreso, many studies have confirmed the connection between organisational support, in the form of training and development opportunities, and employee commitment. For example, Olajo and Oyeboade (2016) conducted a study on library personnel in selected private university libraries in South-West, Nigeria. They found that providing appropriate training to library personnel, especially training that aligns with the academic library work environment, leads to job satisfaction and increased commitment to the organisation. The authors concluded that there is a positive and significant relationship between organisational support and employee commitment among library personnel.

Theoretically, job characteristics, organisational support perception and employee commitment variables are anchored on Job Characteristics Theory (JCT) by Hackman and Oldham (1976), Organisational Support Theory (OST) by Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison and Sowa (1986) and Three-Component Theory of Commitment by Meyer and Allen (1997) respectively. The Job Characteristics Theory proposed that the intrinsic satisfaction that the individual need to drive commitment is inherent in the features of the job itself and that, jobs can be designed in ways that allow employee derive enjoyment from the job they perform and perceive it as meaningful and valuable. According to this theory, commitment can be influenced by the five core job characteristics: skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback. These five characteristics relate with structure of psychological climate at work. Based on this theory, if librarians find their job challenging, meaningful, and allowing them to utilise their expertise, they are more likely to be committed to their work.

The Organisational support theory suggests that when employees feel that their input is appreciated and that their well-being is supported and cared for, they are more likely to be motivated and develop a sense of belonging and reciprocate it in a positive manner (Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison & Sowa, 1986). In other words, employees develop positive feeling, perform better and actively involved in organisational goals, when they perceive support and care from the organisation. As a matter of fact, Babalola, Alegbeleye, and Adegbaye (2020) and Kadiri, Elaho (2023) tested the OST in their different studies, they established that support from supervisor and management, and positive relationship with co-workers are factors that contribute to high perceived organisational support and this affect employee commitment.

The Three-Component Theory of Commitment proposed that an employee can be committed in three ways namely affective, continuance, and normative. An affectively committed employee is motivated by their own desire to stay with the organisation (Meyer and Allen, 1997). Continuance commitment, on the other hand, is based on the perception of how much employees feel they have to stay with the organisation. Normative commitment is characterised by a sense of moral obligation to remain in the organisation, as explained by Meyer and Allen (1997). The relevance of this theory lies in the fact that library administrators could potentially discern the three types of commitment among their staff. This understanding would enable them to determine the most suitable incentives to motivate their personnel to perform optimally and demonstrate dedication to both the library and the larger institution.

Methodology

This study employed the survey research design. The population of the study consists of 515 librarians working in the public university libraries in the South-South zone of Nigeria. The participants were drawn using census method. The instrument for data collection was questionnaire. A pre-test was carried out to establish the validity and reliability of the instrument. The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients obtained for the constructs fall between the ranges of 0.87 and 0.96, indicating internal consistency. Out of the 515 copies of questionnaire administered to participants, a total of 415 copies of the questionnaire were returned, but only 400 were found usable for the study. The data were subjected to correlation and multiple regression analysis to establish the correlation among the variables and the combine influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Results

Statistical analysis was carried out on the (400) copies of questionnaires retrieved from participants. To test the formulated hypothesis for this study, both correlation and regression analysis were applied.

Testing Hypotheses

H₀1: Job characteristics and organisational support perception have no significant relationship with librarians' commitment to service delivery in public universities in South-South Nigeria.

Table 1: Mean, Standard deviation and correlation matrix showing the relationship between Librarians' commitment to service delivery, job characteristics and organisational support perception

	Variables	Correlations			Mean	SD	Sig	Remark
		1	2	3				
1	LC	1	.370**	.488**	3.50	1.172	0.000	Sig
2	JC	.370**	1	.557**	4.01	0.970	0.000	Sig
3	OSP	.488**	.557**	1	3.62	1.133	0.000	Sig

(** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), N=400; LC = Librarians' commitment; JC= Job characteristics; OSP =organisational support perception)

Correlation values of 0–0.30, 0.31–0.60, and 0.61–1.00 corresponds to small (weak), moderate, and large (strong) relationships (AlWahaibi, AlHadabi, & AlKharusi, 2020).

The results in Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of all the variables, which indicate an existence of high level mean score of JC, POS and LC. The Pearson zero order correlation result reveals that librarians' commitment to service delivery had positive and significant relationship with job characteristics ($r = 0.370$, $N=400$, $p < 0.05$) and organisational support perception ($r = 0.488$, $N=400$, $p < 0.05$). In addition, while the relationship between job characteristics and librarians' commitment shows a weak positive relationship as indicated by $r = 0.370$, organisational support perception and employees' commitment to service delivery relationship shows a moderate, but positive relationship ($r = 0.488$). Based on this, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This implies that the level of librarians' commitment to service delivery in public Universities in South-South Nigerian is related to their job characteristics and perception of organisational support.

H₀2: Job characteristics and organisational support perception have no significant joint influence on librarians' commitment to service delivery in public universities in South-South Nigeria.

Table 2: Multiple linear regression analysis of the joint influence of job characteristics and organisational support perception on librarians' commitment to service delivery (N=400)

	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	't' Value	Sig.	Adj. R ²	F	DF	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta						
						0.245	65.671	2, 397	0.000

S/ n	(Constant)	1.56 1	0.195		7.996	0.000	(24.5)			
1.	Job characterist ics	0.15 5	0.057	0.143	2.733	0.007				
2.	Perceived organisatio nal support	0.36 2	0.047	0.404	7.716	0.000				
Dependent Variable: Librarians' Commitment to Service Delivery										

(Figures parentheses indicate percentage)

Sig. at $p < 0.05$

Note: β = Standardised coefficient

The regression model in Table 2 indicates that JC and OSP together in one model had significant influence on LCS D ($Adj.R^2 = 0.245$, $F_{(2,397)} = 65.671$, $p < 0.05$). Specifically, Table 2 shows both the relative and joint influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The model reveals that OSP ($\beta = 0.404$, $t = 7.716$, $p < 0.05$) offered more contribution to LCS D than JC ($\beta = 0.143$, $t = 2.733$, $p < 0.05$). In addition, the two variables jointly accounts for 24.5% ($Adj.R^2 = 0.245$) of the variance in librarians' commitment to service delivery. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that job characteristics and organisational support perception have no significant joint influence on librarians' commitment to service delivery in public universities in South-South Nigeria, was rejected by this finding. This implies that the dependent variables were significant predictors of librarians' commitment to service delivery in public universities in South-South Nigeria.

Discussion of findings

This paper investigates the nexus between job characteristics, organisational support perception and librarians' commitment to service delivery in public universities in South-South Nigeria. The findings of the correlation analysis revealed that job characteristics, organisational support perception and librarians' commitment to service delivery are positively and significantly related. This implies that there is a positive and significant connection between how an employee's job is designed to make him/her feel satisfied with the job itself and how he/she perceives the support given by the organisation and their decision on whether to attach to the organisation and its goals and values or not. Although the relationship between job characteristics and librarians' commitment was weak, the relationship between organisational support perception and librarians' commitment was moderately strong. In comparing both independent variables, organisational support perception correlates more strongly with librarians' commitment than job characteristics. The result of the relationship between JC and LCS D is supported by the finding of Thirunavukarasu and Sritharan (2016), who found a positive relationship between job characteristics and the organisational commitment of employees working in Cuddalore town private industries.

The regression analysis results reveal that job characteristics and organisational support perception jointly influenced librarians' commitment to service delivery in public universities in South-South Nigeria. These two variables, examined together, explained 24.5% of the variance in librarians' commitment to service delivery in public universities in South-South Nigeria. This implies that librarians' commitment to service delivery is strengthened when their job contains certain characteristics (skill variety, task identification, task significance,

autonomy and feedback) together with having a perception that they are being supported through various caring activities in the organisation (either from the top management, supervisor or co-workers). However, organisational support perception contributed more to librarians' commitment than job characteristics. This is in line with Ahmad (2018), who found that employees tend to value the extrinsic rewards of their jobs more than the intrinsic benefits. At this point, it is important to note that while there are studies that separately examine the impact of job characteristics and perceived organisational support on employee commitment, it appears that no known research has investigated the combined effect of these two factors on employee commitment. As a result, it lacks literature to support it. The present study has provided lucid evidence that core job characteristics enhance librarians' commitment to service delivery. The finding of this study finds support in previous literature that factors that contribute to employee attitude and behaviour centre around the job content or work-itself (job characteristics; Thirunavukarasu & Sritharan, 2016; Ahmad, 2018; Darma, Purwadi, Sundari, Hakim & Pusriadi, 2020; Jiang, Wang, & Weng, 2022; Wegwu & Princewill, 2023) and factors that has to do with the job context (perceived support from the workplace; Jegede & Ola-Olorun, 2017; Ateke & Akani, 2018; Kadiri & Elaho 2020, Sheikh, 2022).

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study enhances our understanding of the factors influencing employee commitment of librarians working in university libraries in the South-South region of Nigeria. Results of this study reveal that job characteristics and organisational support perception are crucial enhancers of employee commitment among librarians. In other words, for librarians to contribute and develop commitment toward their organisation (university libraries) and its goals through quality service delivery, the job itself must be structured so that it makes them feel a sense of personal fulfilment and satisfaction. It can also be concluded that making librarians feel that they are important by supporting them contributes to their positive perception of the organisation, which, in turn, boosts commitment to the organisation through quality service delivery. The findings implied that librarians are sensitive to how their job is structured to meet employees' needs and a supportive work environment that values employees' contributions, which the findings of this study have established as influencers of librarians' commitment. Thus, it is important that the management supports the employee by prioritising their job characteristics, welfare and work environment. Based on the findings of this study, it is therefore recommended that university library management ensure that librarian's job is well designed to contain core characteristics that enrich their job and make them feel satisfied with their jobs. Library management should create an enabling and supportive environment, as this will encourage supervisors to support their subordinates and colleagues supporting their fellow colleagues as a way of fostering commitment among librarians. Also, library management should provide feedback and recognise librarians' excellent performance.

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